

Determination of Differential Diffusion Coefficients of Magnesium Nitrate by the Diaphragm Cell Method

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Diffusion coefficients of magnesium nitrate in water in the concentration varying from 0.05–0.14 M have been determined by a modified form of diaphragm cell. The experimental results indicate a good agreement with the theoretical results obtained from the Onsager and Fuoss theory.

INSPITE of the scarcity of experimental data of diffusion coefficients, it has been possible to develop an exact theory of diffusion for very dilute solutions of the electrolytes. Since the diffusion coefficients vary with the electrolyte concentration, it may be theoretically possible to compute such variations for dilute solutions because of the fact that the nature of the forces between the ions are known. However, in the case of concentrated solutions, since the short range forces of interaction between the ions and the solvent are such that the net influence of all of them cannot be predicted by coulombic interaction alone, no exact theory has been able to explain all the factors involved.

It was, therefore, considered desirable to undertake the present investigations with a view to determine the diffusion coefficients of magnesium nitrate in dilute solutions and to analyse the results in the light of the theory of Onsager and Fuoss¹.

Material and Methods

Magnesium nitrate of A.R. quality was used. Mercury A.R.B.D.H. was used so that the impurities were not more than 0.01 per cent. The solutions were made in conductivity water having a conductance of $\sim 10^6$ mhos/cm.

The diffusion coefficients were determined by a modified form of the diaphragm diffusion cell of G-4 porosity as described by Sanni and Hutchison². The iron sealed stirrers^{3,4} were provided to remove the stagnant layer of the liquid adhering to the surface of the diaphragm. A stirring device using magnetic stirrers at 56 RPM was used. The conductance of the solutions in the upper compartment was measured at regular intervals of time by conductivity bridge (Yellow Spring Instrument Co., Ohio, U.S.A.). The high vacuum stopcocks were all spring loaded. The volume of the pores of the diaphragm cell was determined first by weighing the

diaphragm when dried and then soaking it with pure water and weighing again.

The diffusion cell was calibrated with decinormal potassium chloride diffusing into pure water. The integral values of diffusion coefficients of the diaphragm cell were then evaluated with the use of the equation :

$$-D\beta t = \ln \frac{\Delta C_f}{\Delta C_0} \quad \dots (1)$$

where,

D = diaphragm cell integral diffusion coefficient.

β = diaphragm cell constant and

$$= \frac{A}{l} \left\{ \frac{1}{V_1} + \frac{1}{V_2} \right\}$$

A = area available for diffusion

l = average effective pore length

V_1 and V_2 = volumes of the two compartments

t = time of diffusion

ΔC_0 = initial concentration difference between the two compartments.

ΔC_f = final concentration difference between the two compartments.

The integral values of diffusion coefficients were next converted to the more fundamental differential diffusion coefficients (D) by the use of the equations of Stokes⁴.

$$\bar{D} = \frac{\bar{D}^0(c_m')}{(1 - C_m''/C_m')} - \frac{C_m''}{C_m'} \frac{\bar{D}^0(c_m'')}{(1 - C_m''/C_m')} \quad \dots (2)$$

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and

$$D = \bar{D}^0 + \frac{\sqrt{C}}{2} \cdot \frac{d\bar{D}^0}{d\sqrt{C}} \quad \dots (3)$$

Results and Discussion

According to the theory of Onsager and Fuoss¹ the differential diffusion coefficient D , of an electrolyte may be calculated by the equation :

$$D = (\gamma_1 + \gamma_2) 1000 RT (\bar{m}/C) \left(1 + C \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{\partial C} \right) \quad \dots (4)$$

where the term

$$\begin{aligned} \left(\frac{\bar{m}}{C} \right) &= 1.0748 \times 10^{-20} \frac{\lambda_1^0 \lambda_2^0}{\gamma_1 |Z_1| \Lambda^0} \\ &- \frac{(|Z_2| \lambda_1^0 - |Z_1| \lambda_2^0)^2}{|Z_1 Z_2| (\gamma_1 + \gamma_2) (\Lambda^0)^2} \cdot \frac{3.132 \times 10^{-19} \sqrt{\tau}}{\eta_0 (\epsilon T)^{3/2} (1 + ka)} \\ &+ \left(\frac{Z_2^2 \lambda_1^0 + Z_1^2 \lambda_2^0}{\Lambda^0} \right)^2 \frac{9.304 \times 10^{-13}}{\eta_0 (\epsilon T)^2} C \phi(ka) \end{aligned} \quad \dots (5)$$

and

$$\left(1 + C \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{\partial C} \right) = 1 - \frac{1.1514 S_{(f)} \sqrt{C}}{(1 + A' \sqrt{C})^2} + 2.303 BC - C \psi(d) \quad \dots (6)$$

where

$$\psi(d) = \frac{(d/\partial C) + 0.001(3M_1 - M_2)}{d + 0.001C(3M_1 - M_2)} \quad \dots (7)$$

where M_1 and M_2 are the molecular weights of solvent and solute, d , the density.

In these equations R is the gas constant in ergs per degree per mole, T , the absolute temperature, C the concentration in moles per litre, y_{\pm} is activity coefficients on the molar concentration scale, λ_1^0 and λ_2^0 are the limiting equivalent conductances of the ions of the electrolytes, $\Lambda^0 = \lambda_1^0 + \lambda_2^0$, Z_1 and Z_2 the valency of the +ve and -ve ions, τ , the ional concentration, η_0 , the viscosity of water, ϵ , its dielectric constant, k , the Debye and Hückel reciprocal radius, a , the mean distance of closest approach of the ions and $\phi(ka)$, the exponential integral functions of the theory.

Taking $\eta_0 = 7.208 \times 10^{-3}$, $\lambda_1^0 = 64.33$, $\lambda_2^0 = 84.29$, $\epsilon = 75.04$, $T = 308.16$, $ka = 2.5544 \sqrt{C}$, $S_{(f)} = 1.7983$ for magnesium nitrate and substituting these values in equation (4) to (7) one gets the following numerical equations :-

$$\begin{aligned} D &= 7685 \times 10^{-11} \left(1 + C \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{\partial C} \right) \left[196.6 \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{56.89 \sqrt{C}}{(1 + 2.5544 \sqrt{C})^2} + 1757 C \phi(ka) \right] \end{aligned} \quad \dots (8)$$

$$\left(1 + C \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{\partial C} \right) = 1 - \frac{2.070 \sqrt{C}}{(1 + 2.5544 \sqrt{C})^2} + 0.5042 C - C \psi(d) \quad \dots (9)$$

$$C \psi(d) = \frac{-0.15472 C - 0.00345 C^{3/2}}{0.9941 - 0.15472 C - 0.0023 C^{3/2}} \quad \dots (10)$$

The functions (ka) and $\phi(ka)$ were evaluated from the tables given by Harned and Owen⁵.

The observed diffusion coefficients and the theoretically calculated values derived from eq. (8) to (10) for the system magnesium nitrate are shown in Table 1. The calculated limiting value, D_0 is 1.511×10^{-5} cm²/sec. as evaluated by the use of the equation :

$$D_0 = 8.936 \times 10^{-10} T \frac{\gamma_1 + \gamma_2}{\gamma_1 |Z_1|} \left(\frac{\lambda_1^0 \lambda_2^0}{\Lambda^0} \right) \quad \dots (11)$$

TABLE 1—EXPERIMENTAL AND CALCULATED VALUES OF DIFFUSION COEFFICIENTS AT 35°

Conc. (c)	$(D_0 = 1.511 \times 10^{-5}$ cm ² /sec.)			
	(Concentration in moles/litre, D in cm ² /sec.) $\times 10^5$			
	Observed	Calculated	D'	$(D_0 - D)$ calc.
0.05	1.3380	1.3504	1.4986	0.1606
0.06	1.3470	1.3658	1.4922	0.1452
0.07	1.3580	1.3675	1.5015	0.1435
0.08	1.3750	1.3823	1.5037	0.1287
0.09	1.3780	1.3930	1.4960	0.1180
0.10	1.3900	1.3966	1.5044	0.1144
0.11	1.3990	1.4045	1.5055	0.1065
0.12	1.4070	1.4102	1.5078	0.1008
0.13	1.4200	1.4317	1.4993	0.0793
0.14	1.4310	1.4380	1.5040	0.0730

$$D' = (D_0 - D)_{calc.} + D_{obsd.} \quad \dots (12)$$

In another approach to check the validity of the Onsager and Fuoss theory the quantity D' defined

TABLE 2—DATA EMPLOYED FOR THEORETICAL CALCULATIONS OF DIFFUSION COEFFICIENTS FOR MAGNESIUM NITRATE AT 35 ± 0.01°

Conc. (moles/litre)	$\phi(ka)$	$1 + C \frac{\partial \ln y_{\pm}}{\partial C}$	$\frac{\bar{m}}{C} \times 10^{21}$
0.05	0.2200	0.8455	207.8304
0.06	0.2050	0.8478	209.6389
0.07	0.1710	0.8513	208.6479
0.08	0.1630	0.8556	210.1677
0.09	0.1500	0.8606	210.6475
0.10	0.1319	0.8661	209.8152
0.11	0.1202	0.8718	209.6133
0.12	0.1099	0.8779	209.3139
0.13	0.1084	0.8841	210.6798
0.14	0.0993	0.8905	210.1448

by eq. (12) should not be a function of the concentration and must be equal to the limiting value, D_0 . The fact that the mean value D' given in Table 1 differs slightly from the limiting value D_0 shows that the theory of Onsager and Fuoss is valid over this moderate range of concentration. The data employed in the evaluation of the theoretical results for diffusion coefficients are recorded in Table 2.

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